

SUGAR PRODUCTION FROM WHEAT STRAW BY HYDROTHERMAL PRETREATMENTS AND ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS

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ABSTRACT: The work target was to compare the efficiency of two hydrothermal pretreatments, viz.: Steam Explosion (SE) and Liquid Hot Water (LHW), towards fractionation of pretreated wheat straw and enzymatic digestibility of the cellulosic residue. The SE and LHW were performed at two severities with and without acidic catalyst (H₂SO₄, 3%). The SE was performed with a batch reactor of 10 L, coupled with a 125 kW boiler. The LHW was carried out with a high pressure and temperature batch reactor (PARR) of a 0.270 l vessel with adjustable internal stirrer and heat control. After SE and LHW pretreatments the materials were extracted by water to remove and quantify the soluble hemicellulose as monomers and oligomers as well the inhibitors; the solid residue was saccharified by enzymatic hydrolysis (EH) at the solids loading of 5% (w/v), 50 °C and pH 4.8 for 72h with a stirring speed of 180 rpm. The residual lignin was determined gravimetrically. As general trend, the digestibility of cellulose was slightly higher with the SE, while LHW allowed higher hemicellulosic sugars recovery in the aqueous fraction.

Keywords: straw; pretreatment; second generation; hydrolysis; biobased economy.

1 INTRODUCTION

The wheat straw (WS) is a widespread agricultural residue that could be used as feedstock for biorefinery applications. In order to valorize this lignocellulosic residue, a pretreatment is necessary to fractionate its components and to improve the cellulose enzymatic hydrolyzability.

Many pretreatments were tested on lignocellulosic biomass for this purpose; among them Liquid hot water (LHW) and Steam Explosion (SE) were widely investigated [1]. The LHW is a hydrothermal pretreatment, where pressure is applied to maintain water in the liquid state at elevated temperature [2]. The SE consists in heating the biomass by high pressure saturated steam for a short time (few minutes), and then the pressure is suddenly reduced to the atmospheric conditions by an “explosive” decompression through a valve [3].

Many works had as subject the treatment of wheat straw with LHW and SE on. Perez et al. have found the treatment conditions with LHW (i.e. 188 °C for 40 min.) which maximizes both the recovery of hemicellulose sugars (44%) and the glucose production after EH (80%) [4].

Other authors have examined the use of SE on straw finding the best treatment conditions at 190 °C and 10 minutes on acid-impregnated straw (sulphuric acid 0.9%) or 210 °C and 6 minutes without acid [3, 5].

However, a literature survey on straw shows that direct comparisons of LHW and SE treatments carried out at the same severity conditions, are rarely reported. The severity of the pretreatment can be semi-empirically reported by the so called ‘severity factor’ Ro, in which the temperature and the duration are combined as follow:

$$Ro = t \cdot e^{((T-T_{ref})/14.75)}$$

with time t expressed in minutes and temperature T in degrees Celsius, the reference state is generally chosen at 100°C and Ro is reported as its decimal logarithm, LogRo [6].

The purpose of this work was to compare the effects of LHW and SE at the same LogRo, on wheat straw, in terms of sugars recovery, in particular of glucose produced after the following step of EH.

The scheme of the process is shown in the Figure 1. Both LHW and SE are applied with and without the addition of acidic catalyst (H₂SO₄ 3%).

The severity LogRo 4.65 was used for the not catalysed treatments, while the lower severity was assumed for the catalysed ones LogRo 3.64 and are referred in the following as c-LHW; c-SE). Both these conditions guarantee higher saccharification yields [3,7].

Preliminary considerations led to exclude the use of more complex parameters like the combined severity factor that include a factor which theoretically should adapt the relationship on the basis of the acid load.

Figure 1: Process scheme.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Raw material

The WS samples (grinded at 0.5-2 cm particle size) were supplied by University of Hull and processed at ENEA Research Center (Italy).

2.2 Liquid Hot Water (LHW) pretreatment

The LHW pretreatment was carried out in 270 mL Parr® Reactor (Autoclave Buchi Limbo Li, Figure 2) loaded with 5 g of WS dry matter, and 100 mL of water or sulfuric acid solution (containing 0.15 g of acid), under stirring condition of 2000 rpm. The temperature was initially set at 204 °C for 30 minutes in the not catalyzed trial and 164 °C for 30 minutes in the catalyzed one. The severity parameter Ro was calculated on the basis of the average temperature, acquired over the entire time interval when the temperature is above 100 °C, ie considering part of the heating and cooling times (see

Results and discussion). After the treatment, the product was filtered to separate the water soluble material (SM, mainly hemicellulose) from the water insoluble material (IM, mainly cellulose and lignin).

2.3 Steam Explosion (SE) pretreatment

The SE was carried out in a 10 liters batch reactor (Figure 3) loaded with WS (500 g of dry matter) humidified with a 0.5 liters solution containing (or not containing) 1.5 g of sulfuric acid. Treatment conditions were chosen in order to have the same severity of LHW, in particular 224 °C, 10 min. for the not catalyzed trial, and 200 °C, 5 min. for the catalyzed one (c-SE). After the treatment, the product was washed with hot water and filtered to separate the water soluble material (SM, mainly hemicellulose) from the water insoluble material (IM, mainly cellulose and lignin).

2.4 Enzymatic Hydrolysis of pretreated WS

The enzymatic hydrolysis (EH) of the IM was performed on citrate buffer (50 mM, pH 4.8) suspension, having 0.5% of dry matter. The enzyme (Cellic CTec2[®], 150 FPU) was loaded as 8% wt of IM. The EH was carried out at 50°C for 72 h, in shaken flasks (180 rpm).

Figure 2: The Parr[®] Reactor used for the LHW.

Figure 3: Steam Explosion batch plant.

2.5 Analytical Methods

The WS and IM were characterized in terms of carbohydrates and lignin contents, referring to the Klason methodology [TAPPI T-13m-54]. The SM was treated with sulfuric acid (2% at 121°C) to depolymerize all the solubilized carbohydrates and detect them as monomers.

The ash content was measured by the combustion of the sample at 600°C.

Sugars contents as well as the glucose amount, after the enzymatic hydrolysis of IM, were determined with a HPIC DX 300 system equipped with a Nucleogel 300. The detector was a Shodex RI101 refractive index.

The inhibitors (Formic acid, Acetic acid, Furfural and Hydroxymethyl Furfural HMF) were analyzed using the HP1100 system equipped with a Dionex AS1 column and a diode array detector. The quantification was carried out at two different wavelengths, 205 and 280 nm.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Severity calculation in LHW

During the LHW tests the temperature was monitored for the time the temperature inside the reactor was above 100 °C, obtaining the profile shown in Figure 4 (blue line; in red the set value).

Using the formula R_0 , the actual severity value was calculated by numerical integration of the curve reported in Figure 5. The values of LogRo 4.65 (not catalyzed) and LogRo 3.64 (catalyzed) were obtained.

In the SE apparatus the temperature reaches the set value in few seconds and the effect on R_0 value of this un-stationary step can be neglected. So, the severities calculated in the LHW and c-LHW cases were reproduced in SE working at 224 °C, 10 min. and 200 °C, 5 min. respectively.

Figure 4: LHW not catalyzed; temperature of the PARR reactor detected during the trial (in red set values).

Figure 5: LHW not catalyzed; differential of R_0 (curve) and R_0 (underlying area) let to determine the actual severity: LogRo 4.65.

3.2 Products analyses and treatment comparison

WS and relative products (SM and IM fractions, obtained after each treatment) were analyzed to quantify their main constituents. Glucose and xylose are reported in Tables I and II as their correspondent polymeric form (glucan and xylan). The acid insoluble residue (AIR) and the amount of each dried fraction are weighted and reported as percentage of WS.

In the Figure 6 are reported the total quantity of produced inhibitors and the main sugars in the hemicellulose solution (containing SM).

In the case of LHW the use of acid slightly improves the recovery of soluble sugar, as expected; while in the SE the recovery of sugars is depressed.

Figure 6: inhibitors and main sugars detected in SM solution (wt% referred to 100 of WS).

This behavior and differences can be explained considering the thermolabile nature of hemicellulose. The acid catalyzed the saccharification of the hemicellulose, but a simultaneous conversion of free sugars (into furans and levulinic acid, etc.) is occurring.

A hemicellulose recovery optimization would require a careful optimization of t, T and acid, but this is beyond the scope of this work.

The lower content of inhibitors that was found in WS from SE compared to the LHW cannot be assumed as measure of their primary production. Indeed, LHW was performed in a closed system that was opened when T reached room values, so ensuring all the volatile components were adsorbed in the liquid phase. On the contrary, SE is based on the pressure release that heavily affected the fate of the inhibitors.

Overall, the higher temperatures used in SE compromised the content of the carbohydrates, which are the half respect to those solubilized by LHW.

Table I: Compositions of WS and products after treatments at high severity without catalyst.

	LHW		SE		
	LogRo	4.65	LogRo	4.65	
	WS	SM	IM	SM	IM
Glucan, %	36	2.9	33	2.3	25
Xylan, %	16.3	9.4	1.0	4.2	0.5
AIR, %	20.3	0	26.0	0	15.7
Other, %	27.4	23.2	3.9	17.1	0.9
total DM, %	100	35.6	63.9	23.6	42

Table II: Compositions of WS and products after treatments at low severity with catalyst (H₂SO₄, 3%).

	c-LHW		c-SE		
	LogRo = 3.64	LogRo = 3.64	LogRo = 3.64	LogRo = 3.64	
	WS	SM	IM	SM	IM
Glucan, %	36	0.9	31	0.9	29
Xylan, %	16.3	11.9	2.9	3.8	0.5
AIR, %	20.3	0	14.9	0	15.7
Other, %	27.4	37.6	3.3	28.4	3.0
total DM, %	100	50.3	52.2	33.1	48

3.3 Enzymatic hydrolysis and sugar recovery

Figure 7 shows the effect of the treatments on enzymatic hydrolysis. The EH yield refers to the conversion degree of the cellulose of IM into glucose. The glucose and xylose yield refer to the percentage of sugars obtained after EH respect the potential obtainable from the starting WS.

The EH yield is higher in the case of SE than LHW, (77-90% EH yield vs 70% of LHW), pointing out the higher digestibility of the SE cellulosic residue. However, if reported to the mass of recovered solid not differences between the treatments are observed in terms of produced glucose that resulted about 1/4 of the starting wheat straw weight.

Xylose yield in the EH step appears generally low because most of this sugar was extracted and recovered in the SM fraction.

In Figure 8 are reported the data of total sugars and the lignin rich solid resulting as residue after EH in the four cases.

In recovering sugars the LHW provided better results, particularly as regard xylan in the aqueous fraction. Overall, the recovered sugars with LHW were about 40% against 30-33% from SE.

The use of acid did not significantly increase the recovery of sugars, neither for LHW and SE. Of course this is referred only to the tested conditions and should not be extrapolated as a general rule. Indeed, it is well known that in several feedstocks the use of acid is required to achieve hemicellulose recovery at low severity.

Acidic conditions in the pretreatment are useful to obtain a digestible substrate, such circumstance is important to reduce the use of expensive enzymes and if a concentrate glucose stream is the main desired product.

Figure 7: Sugars recovery after EH.

Figure 8: Products recovery (wt% referred to 100 of WS).

4 CONCLUSIONS

In terms of sugar recovery LHW provided more interesting results because the recovery was about 40% against 30-33% from SE, the latter pretreatment produced a more digestible cellulosic substrate.

If the value of hemicellulose sugars is the most important criterion, LHW pretreatment would be the recommended one.

In cases where the cost of enzymes and the value of glucose are dominant factors SE has a higher interest.

The situation changes dramatically if practical and economic aspects should be taken into account basically because the duration of LHW pretreatment is much longer, in the order of one hour, while SE only few minutes.

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7 LOGO SPACE

